

Parts of software engineering can be likened to out-of-the-box creation, other parts as science. The latter yield new knowledge codified in a variety of prescriptions and rules. The staggering complexity of modern digital systems means that this body of knowledge is growing past the limit of where education and training can bring the human workforce. AI applications may bring much needed relief in this ambit.

The artificial programmer

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At present, the production of software is not the primary goal for the advances of artificial intelligence (AI) fuelled by compute-hungry deep learning. Yet recent surveys show that AI has found application in virtually all software engineering tasks. To date, this advance has taken place more in requirements engineering and testing, than in implementation and maintenance. This disproportion reflects the fact that the immediate target of AI-based assistance tools in any human production effort, including software development, invariably tends to be routine work. The requirements of engineering and testing tasks are generally acknowledged as the most labour-intensive and the least rewarding because of their introvert slant. This is why they have received earlier attention from AI.

As programming increasingly becomes an integration task and less a clean-sheet creation, however, it is easy to predict that AI will enter and progressively dominate the stage of automated code generation. When that happens, the nature of software design as a speaking-to-the-human prelude to coding will be called into question, while maintenance and refactoring will have to ingest the same “AI-logic” that drives automated code generation. On account of that drive, software engineering will have to transform itself to keep control of trust, traceability, and explainability of the software life cycle being reshaped by AI.

Key insights

- AI-fuelled tools may provide much-desired assistance and relief in virtually all of the software lifecycle processes.
- The software engineering tasks that are more immediately amenable to the application of AI assistance are those that involve routine, repetitive, mechanical work whose execution follows precise rules and mechanisms.
- Software engineering will not go away in the meanwhile: it will transform itself so as to keep control across each individual process and task, and assure trust, traceability and explainability of all the ensuing artefacts.

Key recommendations

- Promote and support the experimentation of AI-fuelled engines to support specific software tasks.
- Promote the augmentation of software engineering guidance in a manner that can exert control and yield assurance over all products of AI-assisted software engineering tasks.
- Machine Learning (ML) experts and Software Engineering experts must team up to ensure AI-assisted software engineering enhances the process and produces high quality software systems.

Introduction

If you are a software engineer, and you are eyeing the flurry of developments in artificial intelligence (AI) with some anxiety because you fear that AI applications might snatch lucrative jobs away from you, rest assured that there is still some journey ahead before that prospect may become reality. In fact, if you are a “true” (i.e. authoritative, trustworthy) software engineer, then you might as well cheer up instead, because your skills will continue to be in high demand – including by AI itself, surprise, surprise – and there are so very few of you around. In fact, instead of taking AI-based software creation as a threat, you may want to regard AI as a most welcome assistant. An assistant ready to take off of you some of the more mundane tasks, the drudgery of software development. And when constructed (or trained) well, AI systems may very well spot relations or solutions that are likely to elude the human gaze. In this way, the human programmer and the artificial programmer should complement instead of battle each other.

As the reader is likely to have experienced, an abundant number of publications claim, or prophesise that the impetuous advancements in the capabilities of AI applications is bound to change the way software is produced. That is certainly true, as we begin to see concrete examples of that happening [1]. The most manifest change applies to the development of user applications that *incorporate* AI engines: arguably, this has been the prime motivation for AI and software production to come together. Less prominent, but still visible in the news has been the development of custom software artefacts *written by* AI, mostly for demonstration purposes. Far less attention, instead, has gone so far to the empowering-by-AI of the software engineering process itself, which is a much broader and more complex concern.

Developing software that applies or uses AI techniques [2] will without doubt ask for a different approach to the software development process than we are used to for traditional software applications. Software engineers will have to master the principles

on which these AI-based applications are built to be able to effectively apply such principles in the corresponding software development. The successful application of neural networks does not solely rely on the ability to use its specialized hardware and software. In fact, several publicly available frameworks ease that job considerably nowadays [24]. What this misses and needs most, instead, is profound software-engineering understanding of how such

networks can be sufficiently and efficiently trained, and actively kept up-to-date.

The skills required to accommodate this novel need differ substantially from what was common practice in software engineering just a few years ago. Luckily, the modern-day software engineer is aided in this respect by the emergence of componentised, reusable AI applications, as for example put forward by fast.ai [3], which

Figure 1: The steps of training an inference model and using the trained model for application purposes. (Source: <https://blogs.nvidia.com/blog/2016/08/22/difference-deep-learning-training-inference-ai/>)

Figure 2: A view of the components of software engineering. (Source: <https://www.zeolearn.com/magazine/the-role-of-artificial-intelligence-in-software-engineering>)

help to realise a structured, less black-box-like approach to the training model.

The desire to make software production closer (not only in time but also in practice) to the end user, without forcing them to become expert programmers, has been around ever since software programs (apps if you will) have been acknowledged as essential commodities. Having AI techniques aid software programming is only the latest, and perhaps the most long-ranging, quest in that direction. Other approaches have emerged in the last few years that have gained some attention, most notably, the so-called no-code/low-code development platforms. It is opportune to understand how they relate to the vision discussed in this article.

Low-code/no-code development is a visual (as opposed to textual) development paradigm. It entails the composition of predefined blocks of code, categorized by a manifest-like description of what they do, and interfaces that allow them to be “hooked up” in a LEGO-like manner to other visual blocks, compatible for interfaces and useful for functionality. The difference between low- and no-code development is the extent to which those blocks are open to changes: the no-code development views such blocks are entirely black-box and does not require (nor allow) changes to their code contents; the low-code development does allow that for some

blocks. While the intent is essentially the same, the difference between them is the target user of the development platform: the no-code style is intended to what is often termed the “citizen programmer” (somewhat of a misnomer, really), a person that wishes or is expected to produce running software programs without needing any training in programming.

The common trait of both variants is that they conceive software programs as black-box artifacts, which do not have to be looked inside in by their “developer”. While this may be an attractive commodity in certain business situations where agility is central, it would be rather irresponsible to suggest that such products can be depended upon blindly where serious value (social, economic, ethical) is at stake. The user of AI techniques in software development should be aware of the problem of explainability that is beginning to differentiate “obscure” (potentially hazardous) from “explainable” AI, whose algorithms humans can comprehend and trust. We surely want the latter and should direct effort to enabling it that way.

Artificial intelligence and software development

As noted earlier, it is opportune to make a distinction between the use of AI in software and the use of AI in *software development*. This article focuses on the latter. The

expectation that human programming will be obsolete in some (near) future seems to dwell on the expectation that AI-based applications will produce the software program code that, to date, is still the output of a human programmer.

Before we dive into the reality of this prediction, we should recall that software engineering is far more than just coding: it also comprises design, verification and maintenance (see Figure 2). Coding, that is, the act of producing program text (a.k.a. source code) is the culmination of a thinking process, and there is no substitute for it. Likewise, delivering source code is for a software engineer not just to commit algorithmic concepts to program text, but to verify that the execution yields correct results, in both functional (what it computes) and non-functional (how it does so) terms, and to make sure the corresponding logic transpires from said text, so that future maintenance efforts shall not be mystified.

In that respect, therefore, a more ambitious (and futuristic) title of this article might have been: “The Artificial Software Engineer”, as opposed to “Programmer”, to reflect the oft-forgotten understanding that writing program text is only a fraction of the software engineering deeds, and frequently not the most important one (while certainly the most visible), as counter-intuitive as that may seem. Useful, good software has many happy users, is frequently used, yields satisfaction, and consequently has a long lifetime. It therefore addresses the user needs well, works well, and is designed and coded well. Few software programs have all of these qualities at once, across professional, institutional, social, and personal ambits. This rather frustrating state of affairs is not surprising since the total number of “true” software engineers worldwide still is very modest as yet, even 52 years after the discipline was first conjured into existence [4].

More modestly and perhaps more realistically, then, the title of this article is “The Artificial Programmer”. This down-casting from grander ambition reflects the fact that current AI is applicable, and has been applied already, to an increasing

fraction of the software-engineering stages referred to earlier, but so far in an isolated and segmented manner, i.e. covering more the production of specific development artefacts (hence vertically) than seamlessly supporting larger tracts of the overall software lifecycle, from conception to retirement (hence horizontally). It is comparatively easy to predict that the current trend of vertical progress will thrive: commercial reasons, quest for public resonance, and appetite for the here-and-now provide abundant fuel to vertical-driven efforts, some of which admittedly have achieved fascinating results [5]. A much grander ambition is to create an integrated, AI supported software development process, where the contribution of AI, probably more in its “strong” acceptance than its “weak”, vertical, form, may span across all development activities, in manners that may probably also change the nature of the corresponding products.

Below, we consider each of the five software engineering stages in isolation: requirements engineering, design, implementation, testing, and maintenance. In doing so, we take inspiration from recent reviews [6,7].

Requirements engineering (RE)

RE is the activity of defining what a system is supposed to do, which problems it should help solve or which tasks it should execute. Such requirements are most often defined by the customers (perhaps with little or no understanding of software) using natural language. As the requirements as stipulated drive all of the subsequent development (design and implementation, but also verification and maintenance), they must capture the intentions of the customer (and prospective user) correctly and consistently.

An overlooked, incorrectly specified, or superfluous requirement may result in costly corrections in later stages of the project lifecycle, if not even in a failed product. Also, requirements must be consistent (i.e. sound, agreed, free from contradiction, without abrupt changes), and must be kept so when changes are applied. If requirements are specified using natural language,

then it is very important that the language used for them is very carefully crafted, to avoid confusion, ambiguity, inconsistency, etc. That is often hard on the customer. Using specialized formalisms is less exposed to that risk, but that is an expert task, more suited for the supplier and scarcely so for the customer, liable to create undesirable intellectual distance between supplier and customer. Moreover, whatever the chosen form, keeping the requirement specification correct and consistent all along the development process drains precious energy from the productive side, so it is frequently neglected or relegated to an admin duty.

Undoubtedly therefore, AI techniques, especially natural language processing (NLP), may considerably help the activities of the RE stage. A complicating factor, however, is that requirements are often silently specified in the context of the application domain of the system being developed. In other words, a large fraction of the background information needed to interpret requirements correctly is assumed to be known and not written down explicitly. That makes it necessary for prospective AI-fuelled RE tools to embed a substantial amount of domain knowledge. The effort required to build such domain knowledge is reminiscent of the goals of ontology research, long associated with the so-called semantic web [8] or with the metamodels that underpin model-based or model-driven development [9]. The results that transpire from vocal assistants or chatbots showcase the potential that

can be unleashed in this ambit, provided that sufficient resources, for computing hardware, data sets, and test oracles (a.k.a. tagging), are deployed to this end.

Design

While requirements state the problem, the subsequent stage conceives and realises a solution for it. In classic software engineering, with humans as the development actors, the conception stage (a.k.a. design) is paramount, in that it results in several essential benefits. It helps break the bigger problem into multiple, simpler parts (which eases verification), and determines how such parts can be joined together into the final product (which guides integration). It allows reasoning on how well the proposed solution fits under the project metrics of interest, ahead of committing it to code (which promotes correctness-by-construction in place of costly correctness-by-correction). It allows multiple programmers to work together, consistently on separate and non-conflicting coding tasks (which speeds development).

Whereas primordial design “invented” software solutions, modern design applies various kinds of patterns, increasingly following “blueprints” with good, proven properties, which fit the need as seen by the solution architect. Historians of software engineering attribute this radical change of attitude to the influence exerted by the publication of *The Timeless Way of Building* by Christopher Alexander’s (a true, non-software, architect) in 1979. It took

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Figure 3: Dilbert’s view of the chasm between the user needs and the analyst’s understanding of requirements.

ranging from recurrent boilerplate to business- or domain-specific [18]. This promise still stands, and retains its attractiveness. Not surprisingly, current research in that ambit contemplates AI augmentation to increase the capabilities and reach of automated code generation. Taken all together, these observations suggest that the need for human coding is rapidly declining and likely destined to vanish.

Some demonstrations of automatically coding AI-programs are indeed impressive; for example the OpenAI Codex Live Demo [22]. That engine is based on GPT-3, a neural network trained to understand natural language, and additionally trained with a large number of GitHub repositories containing Python code. At the time of writing, it was able to turn a request stated in natural language into corresponding program code with a 37% chance of success. The way the OpenAI Codex was developed does, however, point to a fundamental hurdle in its conception. As it was trained on 54 million GitHub repositories [23], it effectively “learned” from a very heterogeneous collection of code of varying levels of quality; in other words, it was trained with an unfiltered training set. That will certainly influence the quality of the code produced by the Codex. To increase the standard would require training with code of known good quality. But who can do the filtering of 54 million GitHub repositories? That in itself is a daunting task that cannot be done by humans. Some of that work could be done by coding quality checkers, but such tools look for coding patterns that are known to be dangerous, but not necessarily wrong. Even if an automatic coding tool were trained with high-quality code, extensive verification and validation should be made on its product and on its maker before final acceptance. This drive shifts the burden from implementation to testing, at least for the foreseeable future, until sufficient confidence is gained in AI-fuelled automatic coding tools.

The approach taken by OpenAI in the development of their Codex, much like in most AI efforts to date, may be regarded as a brute-force method. The “model” inside

it does not contain a “model of programming” in the ontological sense of it.

MuZero, a recent development of DeepMind, and the successor to AlphaGo, generates internal models all by itself by studying training sets. Such models are then used to execute goal-oriented and rule-based tasks, e.g., playing a game of chess, Go, or even playing an arcade style video game. Recently, DeepMind released AlphaCode, an AI-based system which leverages DeepMind’s technology for automatic coding of problems described in natural language [28] [29]. AlphaCode was trained with many problems and solutions from GitHub, and from Codeforces [31], a website hosting programming competitions. After training, AlphaCode was entered as a contestant in 10 new Codeforces competitions, programming challenges that were outside of its training set. It acquired a surprising level of 54% as compared with human contestants. AlphaCode acquired this level by generating a large set of Python and C++ programs from a problem description, ranking the solutions, and then presenting the top 10% most promising solutions to humans who assessed them and submitted the best. So, yes, there were still humans involved, but not in the creative step of generating solutions. However, another noteworthy result is the fact that AlphaCode is comparatively good at solving competition-type challenges, but performs rather poorly on introductory-problem type challenges [30]. It appears that AlphaCode was overtrained for the former, and became too “smart” to solve the latter, again showing that the training set of an ML system is crucial for its performance.

Both OpenAI’s and DeepMind’s developments show impressive progress in automatic coding from natural language problem descriptions, and show at the same time the limitations of the approaches.

The darker side of coding is *refactoring*, whether before product release or as part of post-release maintenance. Refactoring is the process of modifying the structural organization of existing program code without changing functional behaviour, to improve performance or better conform with quality standards. The biggest drag

on such work is when the program logic (its rationale) does not transpire sufficiently well from the program text. This hindrance makes refactoring one of the most expensive parts of software implementation. The root causes of such a problem are more easily attacked by removing arbitrariness from human programming: one route to that end is to lean increasingly on machine-assisted code generation, including the modernisation of legacy code [19]; the other is to use tool assistance, for example code-smell [20] detectors, to help the human programmer to deliver higher-quality program code.

Verification

As E.W. Dijkstra would have it, the endeavour of making a thing (a software program) that satisfies stated needs should be split into two cohesive tasks: (i) stating the properties of a thing, by virtue of which it would satisfy our needs, and (ii) making a thing that is guaranteed to have the stated properties [21]. Verification is the software-engineering process that helps achieve such guarantees.

Verification takes two forms: one is static, that is, it is carried out without requiring execution of the object of verification; the other is dynamic, and it is carried out by what we know as testing. Attention to static analysis is growing: its true potential is still not fully revealed as it requires cohesive cooperation between all tools used for specification, design and implementation. It is therefore premature for AI to usefully address that field.

Testing, on the other hand, has been around for much longer. It aims to verify that the right system was built, thereby meeting all due requirements on the input-output relationship under all circumstances and across the complete program-code logic. Releasing software products without thorough testing is utterly irresponsible and incurs consequences ranging from embarrassment to serious damage. Yet achieving high-coverage testing for modern systems has become largely impractical.

The prime hindrance to the desired exhaustiveness is the staggering complex-

Software fails in 2017

606
software fails

\$1.7
trillion

3.6 billion
affected users

268 years
in downtime

ity of modern systems, both vertical (from the stacking of abstraction-building layers) and horizontal (from the increasing specialization of functional algorithms). The biggest obstacle to testing beyond the unit level is the exponential complexity of part interaction, which gives rise to phenomena that may superficially appear as non-deterministic.

Testing is more than finding software faults (the proverbial bugs); it is also about assuring quality, reliability, performance, robustness, and, increasingly, security. Despite a growing number of automation tools that support the execution of software testing, achieving high coverage in all those verification respects – which is expected for business- or mission-critical software – remains a very difficult objective. Conceiving tests is as effort intensive as software design. “Planting” test automation hooks in the program source code requires additional effort to normal programming. Running tests can only be done when the program code exists: when this is late in the project schedule (which is frequently the case), resources begin to be scarce and therefore the relative cost of software testing becomes dominant and therefore subject to affordability trade-offs.

In addition to adopting practices that anticipate software testing (for example, as in test-driven development), all ways of machine-intelligence assistance to software verification are much desired. AI can help in various ways in this regard. It may help translate test specification from natural language to coded test cases. It may deploy genetic algorithms and swarm optimisation techniques in white-box testing and black-box testing. It may guide regression testing by helping to single out the strictly minimal set of test cases that match the extent of the changes. It may help trial user interfaces and stress-test distributed web-based applications. It may automate the analysis of test results across development cycles to predict the likelihood of the future reappearance of already seen failures. And, increasingly, it may help verify the adherence of the final software product to the stated system requirements, e.g., by model-based testing [25].

Maintenance

AI-tools used in the maintenance phase focus on aspects that range from extracting information from user product reviews to the classification of bug reports. Knowledge-based systems are applied to establish the maintainability of software, and to plan software maintenance. An important class of AI tools in maintenance are formed by assistants that help the software engineer find his or her way in the source code base of an application, guided by a particular problem that has to be solved. AI-based software refactoring tools also play an important role in this phase. Other tools are able to discover, or reconstruct the interface state model of software components by observing the component’s behaviour, either when in use (passive model inference) or by exercising the component (active model inference). Interface behavioural models thus derived are subsequently used for refactoring and testing software components. Such models can also be used to identify gaps in existing sets of test cases [26]. The techniques are based on computational learning theory (or just learning theory), a lesser known subfield of artificial intelligence devoted to studying the design and analysis of machine learning algorithms.

Summing it up

The source cited in reference [7] reports that, as of July 2020, 28% of the works on the application of AI in software engineering address requirements engineer-

Figure 5: some figures that tell how much wanted is thorough software testing.

(Source: <https://medium.com/@elena.gumenyuk/you-dont-need-software-testing-do-you-9c0f0809da95> Data for the year 2018 can be found at <https://spectrum.ieee.org/riskfactor/computing/it/it-failures-2018-all-the-old-familiar-faces>)

ing, 12% design, 9% implementation, 42% testing, and 9% maintenance. This review evidence suggests that requirements engineering and testing are the most popular areas for the application of AI techniques, whereas implementation and maintenance still lag behind. These proportions may reflect the fact that requirements engineering and testing project a routine yet effort-intensive nature, while implementation is associated – increasingly inaccurately as we have noted earlier – with a far more creative endeavour. Overall, the conception of AI-based assistance tools for software development generally tends to take over as much routine work from the software engineering tasks as possible. As in all cases of automation, the premise to that movement is to make more time available for human creativity.

Parts of software engineering can be regarded as outside-the-box creation, other parts as science. The scientific aspects of software engineering yield rules and counsels with various degrees of rigour, dos and don’ts, best practices, things that can be formalized. The staggering size and complexity of software systems, and the rising proportion of extra-functional requirements cause the body of such rules and counsels to grow accordingly. This in turn makes their diligent application more complex and daunting and labour intensive. AI applications can and do bring much needed relief in this situation.

The more “artistic” side of software engineering, where thinking outside-the-

box and creativity is required, is a challenging application area for AI-based software engineering tools. ML applications will certainly be able to find unforeseen relations in programming techniques to come up with new programming solutions, but coding outside-the-box is still a bridge too far.

What about hardware design?

Decades ago, hardware designers created systems by drawing gates and connections among them, and applying advanced Boolean algebraic techniques to find the optimal circuit. That line of work was akin to electronic (as opposed to informatics) design methods. It was a slow, tedious and error-prone job. Then, in the mid-1980's, hardware description languages (HDL) took off.

With the advent of productive HDLs such as Verilog's and VHDL's programming environments, hardware design departed from electronic design and started to look more like software programming.

In the early days of computer making, not only did the design of the hardware itself play an important role, but its material implementation also required a lot of attention by the designer. As the functionality of hardware design tools progressed, more and more of these tedious tasks were automated, which is a common trait of all engineering processes. Yet finding the optimal hardware design remains a compute-intensive task, which quickly grows beyond the capabilities of even modern conventional computers. Owing to that, heuristics were devised to find good-enough (not necessarily optimal) designs. With the unabated growth in size and complexity of modern digital systems, however, even heuristics don't cut it anymore. Unsurprisingly, therefore, AI-techniques have begun to be used to assist hardware designers, as of late, to overcome the difficulty of optimal circuit design. Even in that new style, the functionality of the hardware circuit is described by the designer in the form of an HDL program.

Important forces resist revolutions in industrial production, however. Changing

the way of working is hard for humans, even more so for organisations. Hardware design is often done in a brute-force manner, with circuits designed from the ground up. Circuits are optimised for a particular purpose, and thus are not readily reusable. Circuit design often lacks composability beyond the standard libraries provided by the chip manufacturer. Conversely, modern AI support techniques can be leveraged most successfully for problems that can be divided into smaller composable problems. Circuit design still has to go some way to reach that level.

The question whether AI techniques are likely to emerge that may assist – let alone replace – the hardware designer in actual circuit design is relevant and wholly pertinent to the HiPEAC community. In trying to answer it, though, one should appreciate how that event may be more revolutionary than evolutionary. The reasons for that are manifold, but the essence is that hardware production is very costly indeed. Turning a chip design into a set of overlaying masks for the lithographic system is a slow, delicate and extremely specialized pipeline. As the number of layers in a modern advanced integrated circuit (IC) can be close to 100, the cumulative cost of the mask set is very high. Only when that cost can be amortized over many IC units may the price per chip become acceptable for the target market.

It therefore follows that the number of redesigns of a chip must be kept very close to zero. That means that hardware designs are most thoroughly tested, far more than software in fact. Alas, the cost of exhaustively testing hardware designs grows exponentially with the complexity of the circuit. If AI techniques were introduced to aid this process, we had better be certain that they do produce circuits that are correct by design and do not risk incurring higher verification or, worse still, redesign effort. (Unless the whole design process were revamped completely and cost of design were to become so small to make repeating it multiple times affordable. This notion, however, is purely conjectural and very far fetched even in a Vision article.)

AI-assisted software engineering and the HiPEAC community

The HiPEAC community is not involved in AI research; its focus is on software development. AI-based software engineering should be viewed as an application of AI, and is therefore of great interest to the HiPEAC community: it will open the way to the development of larger, more complex software-intensive systems of higher quality. HiPEAC, or more generally, Europe, must focus on this important application area of AI, leveraging the results of state-of-the-art AI research.

To reach this goal, developing AI-based software engineering tools should be treated as a joint effort by the software engineering community and the AI-community. These communities complement each other: their cooperation may accelerate and improve on the end result: more complex, but better quality software with a reduced development effort by humans.

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